

VIETNAM CCG NETWORK POLICY BRIEF

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1. INTRODUCTION

Vietnam is a developing country that has only begun its industrialization process over the past three decades and has been heavily impacted by climate change (CC). Despite facing numerous resource-related challenges, Vietnam consistently demonstrates responsibility and proactivity in fulfilling international commitments to respond to CC. Vietnam submitted its Intended Nationally Determined Contribution (INDC) in 2015, signed and ratified the Paris Agreement, and enacted the National Plan to Implement the Paris Agreement in 2016. In November 2020, the Environmental Protection Law was passed by the National Assembly, which includes a chapter on responding to CC that stipulates responsibilities for reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, adapting to CC, and fulfilling international commitments regarding CC.

At the COP26 conference, Vietnam declared, “It will develop and implement robust measures to reduce GHG emissions with its own resources, along with cooperation and support from the international community, especially developed countries, in terms of finance and technology transfer, including the implementation of mechanisms under the Paris Agreement, to achieve ‘net-zero’ emissions by 2050.” Vietnam also joined the commitment to reduce methane emissions by 30% by 2030 compared to 2020 levels; the Global Declaration on Transition from Coal Power to Clean Energy; the Glasgow Declaration on Forests and Land Use, and several other commitments.

Following the COP26 conference, Vietnam established the National Steering Committee to implement the country’s commitments made at COP26, led by the Prime Minister. The committee has been actively directing the development of strategies, action programs, plans, and projects to fulfill Vietnam’s COP26 commitments. Key documents issued by the Government and the Prime Minister include a decree on mitigating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and protecting the ozone layer; a national strategy on climate change (CC) adaptation through 2050; a project detailing tasks and solutions to deploy the outcomes of COP26; an action program for transitioning to green energy, reducing carbon and methane emissions in the transportation sector; a national action plan for green growth for 2021-2030; an action plan to reduce methane emissions by 2030; a list of sectors and facilities required to inventory GHG emissions; a project to develop the carbon market in Vietnam; and a national system for monitoring and evaluating CC adaptation activities. The Minister of Natural Resources and Environment has issued a circular detailing the implementation of the Environmental Protection Law regarding CC response, published a list of emission factors for GHG inventory, and provided guidance for related ministries and sectors on GHG inventory and measurement, reporting, and assessment of GHG emission mitigation. Ministries and sectors are currently developing and finalizing legal regulations, circulars, and technical guidelines for reducing GHG emissions and adapting to CC within their management scope.

In 2022, Vietnam decided to update its Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) based on the NDC submitted to the UNFCCC in 2020, incorporating new elements and efforts to fulfill commitments made at the COP26 conference. In the updated NDC report of 2022, Vietnam proactively proposed to increase its unconditional GHG emission reduction contribution by 2030 from 9% to 15.8%, and its conditional contribution from 27% to 43.5%.

Accordingly, in this policy brief, the Vietnam CCG Network has compiled key policy issues that Vietnamese policy-making bodies are deeply concerned with, aiming towards the goal of net-zero emissions by 2050. Additionally, this report serves as a proposal for the CCG Center to consider and weigh on the key issues in Vietnam in the current context.

The structure of the key policy topics includes:

- + The necessity/importance of the topic
- + Policy landscapes

+ Expected outcomes

+ Target policies

2. KEY POLICY THEMES

2.1. JUST AND SUSTAINABLE ENERGY TRANSITION

Impact statement

Vietnam, along with the international community, has committed to striving to achieve the carbon neutrality goal by 2050 and to pursue a fair energy transition process. Accordingly, the energy transition process must be equitable and based on equality so that developing countries like Vietnam can sustainably transition to a low-carbon economy and establish a trajectory that adapts to climate change. At the same time, the energy transition must consider social, cultural, environmental, economic, and identity aspects to ensure a fair transition, leaving no one behind, and guaranteeing the achievement of sustainable development goals.

➤ Focus theme 2.1.1: Analyzing the impact of the energy structure transition on vulnerable groups in society

Why is it important?

The energy transition process needs to minimize the impact on labor groups and individuals/households (vulnerable) to ensure fairness in accessing resources and fulfilling responsibilities. Accordingly, the energy transition process should particularly pay attention to:

(i) Supporting labor groups and vulnerable households affected by the energy transition process who may not meet the age or skill requirements during the transition; implementing training and retraining for the affected workers.

(ii) Maintaining continuity, stability, and the ability to meet the energy needs at an acceptable price for the community; issues of pricing and diversity of supply are decisive factors for energy security, from a national interest perspective.

(iii) Ensuring livelihoods or the ability to cope with the economic, social, and environmental impacts on some vulnerable labor groups and households. Supporting these groups requires impact assessment, early planning, and synchronized implementation, transparently informing the affected communities and households. Especially for the coal industry and coal power workforce, training and retraining are very necessary, maximizing the new job opportunities created from energy transition projects and programs.

(iv) Developing policies with the participation of affected labor groups to carry out policy planning at all levels and ensure that gender issues, social welfare, green recovery, and skill development are integrated into policies, projects, and programs about energy transition.

Policy landscapes

The platform policies related to this theme include:

- 1) The National Power Development Planning for the period 2021 - 2030, with a vision to 2050 (Power Planning VIII) in Decision No. 500/QĐ-TTg dated May 15, 2023;
- 2) Decision 262/QĐ-TTg dated April 1, 2024, by the Prime Minister approving the Implementation Plan for the National Power Development Planning for the period 2021-2030, with a vision to 2050 (shortly referred to as the Implementation Plan for Power Planning VIII);
- 3) The National Energy Master Plan for the period 2021 - 2030, with a vision to 2050 at Decision No. 893/QĐ-TTg dated July 26, 2023;
- 4) The project to implement the JETP Declaration at Decision No. 1009/QĐ-TTg dated August 31, 2023.
- 5) The decision to establish the JETP Implementation Secretariat at Decision No. 845/QĐTTg dated July 14, 2023, by the Prime Minister and launched at the 4th meeting of the COP26 Steering Committee.

Expected outcomes and target policy

Expected outcomes

- (i) Identify evidence of the impact of energy transition on the livelihoods, employment, income, and social welfare of vulnerable groups in society;
- (iii) Highlight new employment opportunities created by energy transition projects, programs, and labor demands, as well as the required levels of education and skills;
- (ii) Propose appropriate policy mechanisms to directly support affected groups in achieving economic development goals, ensuring progress, and promoting social equity.

Target policies

The anticipated outcomes mentioned above aim to fulfill the key task number 8 "Ensuring equity in energy transition" in the Implementation Plan of the Political Declaration establishing a partnership for equitable energy transition (JETP Declaration) (Decision No. 1009/QD-TTg, dated August 31, 2023).

➤ Focus theme 2.1.2: Completing the policy and legal framework on electricity development, renewable energy development, and energy transition

Why is it important?

Vietnam is a developing country experiencing rapid growth, leading to an increasing demand for energy, particularly electricity. However, domestic energy sources do not adequately meet this demand; energy imports are growing, certain energy security indicators are fluctuating unfavorably, energy infrastructure is lacking and not synchronized, technological proficiency in some energy sectors remains slow to improve, and the energy market's development is not yet sustainable.

Therefore, researching and enacting new mechanisms and policies for renewable energy development is essential to promote the transition to clean energy, electricity trading in the market, including direct electricity trading. It's also important to note that these mechanisms and policies need to be continuous and long-term to guide investment direction for project development. It's necessary to issue consistent standards and regulations for renewable energy, establish reasonable electricity purchase prices based on scientific calculations and balance between sellers and buyers, mobilize domestic capital effectively for energy projects, create maximum favorable conditions for solar and wind power development, and promptly specify technical conditions, connection standards to the power grid, and fire prevention measures. The government should play a role in ensuring supportive policies to promote broad investment.

Policy landscapes

The fundamental policies related to this theme include:

- 1) Resolution 55-NQ/TW on "Strategic orientation for the development of Vietnam's energy sector until 2030, with a vision to 2045," issued on February 11, 2020, which calls for continued diversification of the energy structure by increasing the proportion of gas-fired power and reducing the proportion of coal-fired power, while also exploiting domestic fossil fuel resources.
- 2) The Prime Minister's statement at the 26th United Nations Climate Change Conference (COP26) that Vietnam will strive to achieve carbon neutrality (Net-zero) by 2050.
- 3) Technical reports and Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC 2022).
- 4) Decision No. 500/QD-TTg dated May 15, 2023, of the Prime Minister approving the National Power Development Plan for the period 2021-2030, with a vision to 2050 (Power Development Plan VIII).
- 5) Decision No. 262/QD-TTg dated April 1, 2024, of the Prime Minister approving the Implementation Plan of the National Power Development Plan for the period 2021-2030,

with a vision to 2050 (referred to as the Implementation Plan of Power Development Plan VIII).

- 6) The implementation project of the JETP Declaration approved by the Prime Minister in Decision No. 1009/QD-TTg dated August 31, 2023, which outlines 10 key tasks.

Expected outcomes and target policy

Expected outcomes

(i) Provide support information for the construction of the Amended Electricity Law, improving policies on investment, planning, electricity pricing management, and developing competitive electricity markets; institutionalize development mechanisms to encourage and promote strong development of renewable energy sources;

(ii) Research and develop auction mechanisms, bidding processes for investor selection along with electricity pricing in the process of amending the Electricity Law and refining the competitive electricity market model;

(iii) Propose a mechanism for direct power purchase agreements between renewable energy producers and consuming customers in line with the Amended Electricity Law and the timeline for implementing the competitive electricity market. Research and develop fee regulations for direct power purchase agreements (DPPA);

(iv) Provide information to support the drafting and enactment of laws on renewable energy; Amend the Law on Energy Efficiency.

(v) Propose mechanisms and policies to encourage domestic enterprises to participate in developing renewable energy, developing renewable energy industries, serving domestic and export markets, and developing equipment manufacturing industries for the electricity sector.

Target policies

The expected outcomes mentioned above aim to:

Implement key task number 1 "Completing mechanisms, policies to promote energy transition" in the Implementation Plan of the Political Declaration establishing a partnership for equitable energy transition (JETP Declaration) (Decision No. 1009/QD-TTg, dated August 31, 2023).

Implement some key tasks in the Implementation Plan of the National Power Development Plan for the period 2021-2030, with a vision to 2050.

2.2. DEVELOPING SUSTAINABLE INFRASTRUCTURE AND GREEN TRANSPORTATION

Impact statement

On July 22, 2022, the Prime Minister signed Decision No. 876/QD-TTg approving the Action Program on green energy conversion, carbon emission reduction, and liquefied natural gas in the transportation sector (GTVT). Accordingly, the development of green transportation systems and sustainable infrastructure is a crucial aspect of implementing the Transportation Sector's Action Program. The transition to green transportation will contribute to enhancing energy efficiency, shifting towards electricity use, and adopting green energy for vehicles, equipment, and green transportation infrastructure. However, the challenge of developing green transportation is directly related to infrastructure systems and costs, which is a challenge for countries aiming to develop green transportation. In addition to promoting policies to create a broad legal framework for green energy and green transportation, there is a need for a collaborative ecosystem involving private enterprises.

➤ Focus theme 2.2.1: Inventory, measurement, reporting, assessment, emission reduction of greenhouse gases, and enhancing participation in the VCM/ETS market in the transportation sector

Why is it important?

The list of sectors required to conduct greenhouse gas inventory includes 06 groups of sectors: i) Energy; ii) Transportation, iii) Construction, iv) Industrial processes, v) Agriculture, forestry, and land use, vi) Waste. The list also specifies the Ministries responsible for the sectors within the scope of the 06 groups mentioned above, including the Ministries of Industry and Trade, Transportation, Construction, Agriculture and Rural Development, Natural Resources and Environment. These Ministries are responsible for conducting greenhouse gas inventory, developing plans and implementing emission reduction measures, measuring, reporting, and assessing emission reduction, allocating greenhouse gas emission quotas for sectors under their management as stipulated in Articles 5, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, and 15 of Government Decree No. 06/2022/ND-CP. Prime Minister's Decision No. 01/2022/QD-TTg also stipulates that the entities required to conduct greenhouse gas inventory are facilities falling under the criteria specified in Article 6(1) of Government Decree No. 06/2022/ND-CP, including 1,912 facilities, of which 70 fall within the scope of the Ministry of Transportation's management.

The transportation sector contributes approximately 18% of the national greenhouse gas emissions according to 2016 data. This emission is projected to increase to about 64.3 million tons of CO₂ by 2025 and 88.1 million tons of CO₂ by 2030 without any action. Therefore, to achieve the strong commitments of the Government, conducting greenhouse gas inventory and implementing mitigation measures in the transportation sector are urgent priorities.

Policy landscapes

- 1) The National Determined Contribution (NDC) 2022 update report, where Vietnam has increased its unconditional emissions reduction contribution to 15.8% by 2030 from 9%, and its conditional contribution from 27% to 43.5%.
- 2) The Environmental Protection Law 2020.
- 3) Government Decree No. 06/2022/ND-CP dated January 7, 2022, regulating greenhouse gas emission reduction and ozone layer protection, detailing Article 91 "Greenhouse gas emission reduction," and Article 139 "Formation and development of the carbon market" of the Environmental Protection Law 2020.
- 4) Prime Minister's Decision No. 01/2022/QD-TTg dated January 18, 2022, issuing the list of sectors and facilities required to conduct greenhouse gas inventory.
- 5) Circular No. 01/2022/TT-BTNMT detailing the implementation of the Environmental Protection Law concerning climate change response.
- 6) Prime Minister's Decision No. 876/QD-TTg dated July 22, 2022: Approval of the Action Program on green energy conversion, carbon emission reduction, and liquefied natural gas in the transportation sector.
- 7) Decision No. 1679/QD-BGTVT dated December 22, 2023, "Issuing the Plan of the Ministry of Transport to implement the Action Program on green energy conversion, carbon emission reduction, and liquefied natural gas in the transportation sector.

Expected outcomes and target policy

Expected outcomes

- Developing a toolkit and providing guidance for businesses to measure, report, and assess in the transportation sector; while enhancing understanding of the emissions trading system (ETS) and voluntary carbon market (VCM).
- Establishing legal and technical requirements, along with opportunities for businesses to participate in the emissions trading system and voluntary carbon market in Vietnam's future.

Target policies

The expected outcomes mentioned above aim to provide support information for issuing Circulars regulating the technical requirements for measuring, reporting, assessing greenhouse

gas emissions reduction, and conducting greenhouse gas inventory in the transportation sector; supporting the implementation of initiatives under the Carbon Market Development Project in Vietnam (the Ministry of Finance has submitted Document No. 222/TTr-BTC to the Prime Minister for approval of the Carbon Market Development Project in Vietnam).

➤ Focus theme 2.2.2: Building mechanisms and policies to encourage the development of green transportation infrastructure and vehicle conversion based on "green" criteria

Why is it important?

On July 22, 2022, the Prime Minister signed Decision No. 876/QD-TTg approving the Action Program on green energy conversion, carbon emission reduction, and methane gas emissions reduction in the transportation sector. This program outlines a roadmap for green energy conversion in each mode of transportation, while also requiring maximum mobilization of resources to implement emission reduction tasks and green energy conversion solutions in the transportation sector from now until 2050.

Decision No. 876/QD-TTg clearly states that green energy conversion is the most fundamental and important task in achieving green growth objectives and fulfilling Vietnam's commitments at the 26th Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (COP26). It is also an opportunity for the transportation sector to develop synchronously towards modernization and sustainability, keeping pace with global trends and advanced development levels. The overall goal set by the government is to develop a green transportation system aiming for net zero carbon emissions by 2050. In this regard, from now until 2030, efforts will focus on improving energy efficiency, promoting the conversion to green energy in transportation sectors that are ready in terms of technology, institutions, and resources to fulfill commitments in the Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) and Vietnam's methane emission reduction targets. From now until 2050, there will be a rational development of transportation methods, along with strong implementation of vehicle, equipment, and transportation infrastructure conversion to utilize electricity and green energy, aiming for net zero carbon emissions by 2050.

Policy landscapes

- 1) Decision No. 876/QD-TTg dated July 22, 2022, by the Prime Minister: Approving the Action Program on Green Energy Conversion, Carbon and Methane Emission Reduction in the Transportation Sector.
- 2) Decision No. 1679/QD-BGTVT dated December 22, 2023, "Issuing the Plan of the Ministry of Transport to implement the Action Program on Green Energy Conversion, Carbon and Methane Emission Reduction in the Transportation Sector."

Expected outcomes and target policy

Expected outcomes

(i) Propose mechanisms and policies to encourage the transition to electricity and green energy use: for road motor vehicles, inland waterway vehicles, domestic shipping vessels, and domestic flights; Develop policies to incentivize and support individuals and businesses to switch from fossil fuel-powered transportation to electric and green energy vehicles.

(ii) Develop green transportation infrastructure: Propose mechanisms and policies to attract investors to build electric charging stations, green energy supply stations along the main national highways; Infrastructure for electric charging stations, green energy supply stations for road motor vehicles at seaports, inland waterway ports, airports, bus stations, and train stations.

(iii) Develop technical standards or green standards in transportation activities to improve energy efficiency and reduce GHG emissions. This includes (i) establishing fuel consumption limits for road motor vehicles on a roadmap, aiming to minimize fuel consumption and GHG emissions; (ii) developing standards and regulations on energy efficiency for engines, carriages, inland waterway vessels, and domestic shipping vessels and flights.

Target policies

The expected outcomes aim to fulfill some key tasks of the Action Program on Green Energy Conversion, Carbon Emission Reduction, and Methane Gas Mitigation in the Transportation Sector, as approved by Prime Minister's Decision No. 876/QD-TTg on July 22, 2022.

Focus theme 2.2.3: Financial mechanisms for the transition to green transportation vehicles (environmentally friendly public transportation - electric vehicles)

Why is it important?

Implementing the national program for the development of transportation and environmentally friendly public transportation systems, in the first phase, the focus is on transitioning public transportation vehicles to electric ones. However, in reality, the investment capital for green energy vehicles, such as electric cars, is estimated to be about four times higher than conventional vehicles. For electric buses, the investment cost per vehicle is very high (approximately 7 billion VND per vehicle), putting significant pressure on investment costs and loan interest for businesses. Therefore, although the Green Energy Conversion Program has outlined a transition roadmap, from a business perspective, this roadmap is very challenging because businesses will only invest when there is economic efficiency.

Faced with this reality, the government must have specific support policies, leverage mechanisms to encourage business investment so that the conversion program can achieve its goals as planned. Transport companies need very large capital to invest in transitioning to electric taxis, electric buses, and electric transportation vehicles.

Policy landscapes

- 1) Decision No. 876/QD-TTg dated July 22, 2022, of the Prime Minister: Approving the Action Program on Green Energy Conversion, Carbon Emission Reduction, and Methane Gas in the Transportation Industry.
- 2) Decision No. 1679/QD-BGTVT dated December 22, 2023: Issuing the Plan of the Ministry of Transport to implement the Action Program on Green Energy Conversion, Carbon Emission Reduction, and Methane Gas in the Transportation Industry

Expected outcomes and target policy:

Expected outcomes

(i) Propose mechanisms and policies for preferential capital borrowing, interest rate borrowing, loan term, infrastructure investment (charging stations/fueling stations, transformer stations), accompanied by specific regulations applicable in practice to support and facilitate businesses in investing in the conversion to electric vehicles.

(ii) Propose mechanisms and policies to support businesses' access to Green Credit Fund for green projects, or access to foreign credit funds, international organizations specifically for green development enterprises.

(iii) Propose preferential mechanisms for access to finance, credit; tax incentives... for enterprises manufacturing electric vehicles, electric vehicle batteries, electric vehicle maintenance and repair, and tax exemptions or reductions for importing electric vehicles; investment in recycling, disposal of used vehicles, and batteries.

Target policies

The expected outcomes aim to provide support for the "Development of a national program for the development of transportation vehicles, public transportation systems environmentally friendly, including electric transportation vehicles"; support the drafting of the 2024 Road Traffic Law.

2.3. CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Impact statement

Developing a circular economy is not only about reusing waste and considering waste as a resource, but also about linking economic activities in a calculated way from the outset, thus contributing to innovating the economic model and improving the quality of growth and national competitiveness. At the national level, the implementation of the circular economy will be evaluated on the basis of many specific indicators related to the effective use of resources and materials; energy saving, development of renewable energies; extending the life cycle of products, limiting waste generation and reducing negative environmental impacts; socio-economic efficiency, innovation and sustainability. By focusing on what already exists and changing the design of new products and assets, the development of a circular economy can help Vietnam define a development path to diversify the economy, reduce dependence on imports, and create growth momentum for the private sector based on the "exploitation" of secondary and renewable materials.

➤ Focus theme 2.3.1: Standards for Waste to Energy (WtE)

Why is it important?

The amount of waste generated by households is huge and tending to increase rapidly over time, creating environmental and pollution management challenges. Faced with these pressures, countries around the world are currently actively implementing waste to energy (WtE) treatment models to gradually replace traditional methods of waste management such as landfill, as this type of technology not only provides optimal environmental benefits, but also provides a significant source of energy to help reduce the burden of natural resource depletion. In Vietnam, there has been a gradual shift towards WtE technology for waste incineration and power generation in recent years. For the selection and application of this type of technology, it is necessary to select and develop a set of criteria that can be used to assess and evaluate the effectiveness and suitability of this type of WtE technology in accordance with Vietnamese practice.

Policy landscapes

- 1) The Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment has issued criteria for MSW treatment technology in Article 28 of Circular No. 02/2022/TT-BTNMT dated 10 January 2022. These are the basic criteria as a basis for assessment, evaluation and selection to be applied to all types of MSW treatment technologies in general in Vietnam.
- 2) The Government issued the Prime Minister's Decision No. 31/2014/QĐ-TTg of 5 May 2014 "On the mechanism to support the development of power generation projects using solid waste in Vietnam", which regulates the electricity purchase price for power generation projects using solid waste.
- 3) QCVN 01:2021/BXD - National technical regulations for building design, issued in conjunction with Circular No. 01/2021/TT-BXD of the Ministry of Public Works dated 19 May 2021.
- 4) QCVN 61-MT:2016/BTNMT on "Vietnam National Technical Regulations on Domestic Waste Incinerators", which regulates the basic technical parameters of solid waste incinerators.
- 5) Decision No. 687/QĐ-TTg of the Prime Minister dated 7 June 2022: Approval of the Circular Economy Development Project in Vietnam

Expected outcomes and target policy

Expected outcomes

(i) Propose appropriate criteria to evaluate types of Waste to Energy (WtE) technologies based on 3 pillars (economic, environmental and energy) and can cover all aspects of socio-economic conditions, people's awareness and cooperation, governance capacity, institutions, finance, engineering - technology.

(ii) Proposed financial mechanism for WtE

Target policies

The expected results aim at implementing the key contents of the project "Developing a Circular Economy in Vietnam", contributing to the reduction of greenhouse gas emission intensity by at least 15% by 2030, towards net zero emissions by 2050; providing information for the drafting of the National Action Plan for the implementation of a circular economy in Vietnam.

➤ Focus theme 2.3.2: Managing waste according to the objectives and guidelines for the development of a circular economy

Why is it important?

In Vietnam, circular economy (CE) development has been identified as one of the priority economic models to implement waste management orientation, efficient use of resources, environmental protection and prevention, natural disaster prevention and climate change response in the next stage of the country's development. Vietnam has issued policies and guidelines for CE development in the policy system and legal documents. In particular, there are many articles and clauses that play a role in promoting CE implementation, such as Article 142 of the Law on Environmental Protection 2020, which regulates CE. At the same time, Decree No. 08/2022/ND-CP instructed the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment to develop a National Action Plan and submit it to the Prime Minister for promulgation in order to specify the task of creating a roadmap for CE implementation in the Environmental Protection Law.

The Circular Economy (CE) promotes fundamental links between resource use, waste and emissions and contributes to the integration of environmental (output) and economic (input) policies. Implementing CE will help to minimize the waste generated and reduce the associated economic, environmental and human health burdens. In this important context, applying the CE waste management model is essential for a sound circular economy that transforms the needs of each country towards a sustainable and zero-waste environment.

Policy landscapes

- 1) Environmental Protection Act 2020 and associated guidance
Article 142 of the Law stipulates that ministries, ministerial-level agencies and provincial-level people's committees shall integrate the circular economy from the stage of formulating policies, planning, plans, programmes and development projects, and manage, reuse and recycle waste. Production, trade and service enterprises shall be responsible for establishing management systems and implementing measures to reduce resource consumption, reduce waste and improve the degree of reuse and recycling of waste from the very beginning. From project construction, product and goods design to production and distribution stages.
- 2) Decree No. 08/2022/ND-CP of the Government dated 10 January 2022: Detailing a number of articles of the Law on Environmental Protection, providing more detailed regulations on criteria; regulations for owners of investment projects, establishments, concentrated production, business and service areas, industrial clusters, owners of investment projects in urban areas and concentrated residential areas in the implementation to achieve meet economic criteria.
- 3) Decision No. 687/QĐ-TTg of the Prime Minister of 7 June 2022: Approval of the Circular Economy Development Project in Vietnam.
- 4) Draft National Action Plan on Circular Economy in Vietnam. Accordingly, the draft plan proposed 5 groups of viewpoints, general objectives and 3 groups of specific objectives with indicators to monitor and evaluate the process of implementing circular economy by 2035. The draft plan also sets out 17 groups of tasks and activities with 56 tasks, specific activities under 5 themes, including Raising awareness, knowledge, skills and developing good practices in implementing circular economy (3 groups with 10 specific tasks and activities); Building and perfecting institutions and policies, improving the effectiveness and efficiency of state management of circular economy (3 groups with 6 specific tasks and

activities); Support to promote the application of circular economy in production, business and consumption (5 groups with 19 specific tasks and activities); Waste management to implement circular economy (3 groups with 10 specific tasks and activities); Strengthening connection, cooperation, monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of circular economy (3 groups with 9 specific tasks and activities).

Expected outcomes and target policy

Expected outcomes

- 1) Proposing a financial mechanism to promote investment in technologies for the treatment of solid domestic waste (waste incineration for power generation); waste classification will be linked to investment in modern technology for the development of waste-to-energy facilities.
- 2) Proposing policy mechanisms for the construction, upgrading and operation of domestic wastewater treatment plants in urban areas, concentrated residential areas, industrial parks and artisan villages to ensure satisfactory treatment. environmental technical regulations before discharge.
- 3) Proposing models for the classification of waste types at source at local level to implement recycling and re-use; changing consumer behaviour to environment-friendly products.

Target policies

The expected results aim at implementing the key contents of the project "Developing a Circular Economy in Vietnam", contributing to the reduction of greenhouse gas emission intensity by at least 15% by 2030, towards net zero emissions by 2050; providing information for the drafting of the National Action Plan for the implementation of a circular economy in Vietnam.

➤ Focus theme 2.3.3: Financing mechanism for the implementation of a circular economy to restore rivers

Why is it important?

In addition to the rapid urbanisation process, many wastewater discharges from industrial and agricultural production have impacted and put increasing pressure on the quantity and quality of water sources in rivers, streams and aquifers in recent years. Most stretches of rivers that flow through densely populated areas, industrial zones and artisan villages have been and continue to be polluted to varying degrees. In this context, the recycling and reuse of wastewater and water has become an extremely urgent requirement for efficient and effective water use. A circular economy approach to water use and wastewater treatment will help solve water crises. At the same time, it will help reduce pollution, restore natural ecosystems and the cultural and historical values associated with water sources.

Policy landscapes

- 1) Law No. 28/2023/QH15 of the National Assembly: Law on Water Resources
- 2) Decree No. 02/2023/ND-CP detailing the implementation of some articles of the Law on Water Resources.
- 3) Law on Environmental Protection 2020 and Decree No. 08/2022/ND-CP detailing some articles of the Law on Environmental Protection 2020.

Expected outcomes and target policy

Expected outcomes

(i) Provide information on the current situation of gaps and challenges in mobilising the participation of all stakeholders and society in the implementation of the circular economy.

(ii) Propose financial incentives, such as tax reductions or exemptions, that can encourage companies and industrial estate operators to adopt water reuse/recycling technologies; policies that mandate the reuse of recycled water/wastewater for non-potable uses, including the use of water in industrial processes.

(ii) Propose financial mechanisms for the process of implementing a circular economy to restore rivers.

Target policies

Expected results: Implementation of the key contents of the project "Development of a Circular Economy in Vietnam"; Contribution to the effective implementation of the National Action Plan for the Implementation of a Circular Economy; Policies and regulations for the protection and prevention of water pollution in Vietnam in the coming period, with the aim of restoring degraded, depleted and polluted rivers.

2.4. CARBON MARKETS

Impact statement

The carbon credit market is an important economic and financial tool for managing carbon emissions. Building a carbon market is a concrete step to prepare for major global policies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, allocate emission quotas, exchange carbon credits, and create financial resources. green for enterprises to innovate technology. Accordingly, the carbon credit market in Vietnam needs to be built in accordance with practical conditions and the country's development orientation, international commitments to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and market development trends. global carbon credits; contribute to making the best use of the resources of domestic economic sectors in participating in activities to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Ensure the fair, open, transparent, safe and effective operation of the domestic carbon credit market in accordance with national conditions and international practices; harmonise the interests of entities in the carbon credit market, increase national competitiveness towards low-carbon economic development and green growth associated with sustainable development.

➤ Focus theme 2.4.1: Greenhouse gas inventory for industries / sectors, companies and municipalities

Why is it important?

According to Clause 2, Article 5 of the Government Decree 06/2022/ND-CP, it is stipulated that subjects must reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Decree 01/2022/QD-TTg of 18 January 2022 establishes a list of sectors and entities emitting greenhouse gases (GHG) that must conduct GHG inventories. These are also participants in the future carbon market. Currently, there is only Circular No. 17/2022/TT-BTNMT, which regulates techniques for measuring, reporting, evaluating GHG emission reduction and GHG inventory in the waste management sector, and also provides guidance for other sectors.

The government has also issued regulations to establish a carbon market in Vietnam, and the pilot phase will start in 2025. In order to operate a carbon trading floor, companies must be able to produce carbon credits. This means that there must be 'goods' to sell. To determine how many commodities there are to sell, regulators urgently need to provide comprehensive guidance on how to accurately measure and inventory companies' actual emissions. Based on the determination of the cap and the scope of emissions, the administrative agency will need to allocate emission allowances within the overall prescribed cap. This helps to determine the emission quotas allocated to sectors and companies for free, and serves as the basis for determining whether a company's emissions are in excess or shortfall of its allowed emissions.

Having a toolkit to ensure common rules and standards helps businesses and communities to proactively inventory and practice calculating greenhouse gas emissions at their facilities; from

there, they can balance costs and benefits to choose appropriate strategies, roadmaps and solutions.

Policy landscapes

- 1) The Law on Environmental Protection 2020 provides the basic legal framework for the formation of the carbon market.
- 2) Government Decree No. 06/2022/ND-CP of 7 January 2022 regulating the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and the protection of the ozone layer, detailing Article 91 "Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions glass" and Article 139 "Formation and development of the carbon market" of the Law on Environmental Protection 2020.
- 3) Decision No. 01/2022/QD-TTg of the Prime Minister dated 18 January 2022, promulgating a list of sectors and enterprises emitting greenhouse gases that must conduct a greenhouse gas inventory, clearly defining the role, the responsibility of the business community to participate in the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions according to the roadmap; regulations on greenhouse gas emissions inventory must be implemented from 2023. List of entities participating in the carbon market according to Article 5, Clause 1 of Decree No. 06, This decision will be updated every 2 years. Currently, the list includes 1,912 entities that are required to report GHG inventories, but by 2024, nearly 3,000 entities will be required to conduct GHG inventories.

Expected outcomes and target policy

Expected outcomes

(i) Develop a greenhouse gas inventory toolkit for companies in each sector/industry group so that companies can estimate the costs and benefits for themselves before independent experts carry out the main verification and calculations;

(ii) Develop a systematic set of indicators and procedures for measurement, reporting and verification (MRV); Provide information to support the development of circulars to guide the implementation of MRV in the building, industry, transport and agriculture sectors.

Target policies

The expected results aim to provide important input information to support the development of a circular regulating measurement, reporting and verification (MRV) techniques for greenhouse gas emission reductions and greenhouse gas inventory. industries, sub-sectors and even at the local level. At the same time, these results are also an important basis for the implementation of the Carbon Market Development Project in Vietnam.

➤ Focus theme 2.4.2: Developing a framework for standardising carbon credits according to sectors to help develop the carbon market

Why is it important?

Carbon markets are an important economic tool for promoting the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and combating climate change. It is essential to develop and identify 'core carbon principles' to demonstrate that carbon credits represent real emission reductions. Each type of carbon credit has attributes that are relevant to the individual project or region in which it is implemented. These attributes affect the price of that type of credit, as the role or importance of additional attributes will be valued differently from the perspective of the buyer. Overall, inconsistencies between credit types mean that connecting buyers and sellers is a time-consuming process that makes transactions inefficient. Different standards may have different fees, processes and timelines for registration, authentication, verification and crediting. This can increase transaction costs and administrative burdens for both buyers and sellers of carbon credits, especially for small-scale projects or projects in developing countries. Therefore, standardising these attributes within a common classification framework and for each sector will help sellers, credit marketers and buyers find the types of credits that meet their needs.

Based on the core carbon principles, with additional attributes defined according to the standard taxonomy framework and priced separately, will be the input for pricing transactions, making it easier for companies to implement things like buying large quantities of carbon credits at once (see also RMIT proposal)..

Policy landscapes

- 1) Government Decree No. 06/2022/ND-CP of 7 January 2022 regulating the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and the protection of the ozone layer.
- 2) Draft Project on Carbon Market Development in Vietnam
- 3) Decree No. 107/2022/ND-CP on Pilot Implementation of Transfer of Emission Reduction Results (Sale of Carbon Credits) and Financial Management of Agreements in the North Central Region
- 4) Decision 569/QD-BTNMT on Promulgation of the Plan of the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment to Implement the Action Plan to Reduce Methane Emissions by 2030
- 5) Decision 739/QD-BTNMT on promulgation of the Plan of the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment for implementation of the Project on tasks and solutions for implementation of the results of the 26th session of the Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change.

Expected outcomes and target policy

Expected outcomes

- (i) Develop and propose a set of core carbon principles;
- (ii) Develop a classification framework and carbon credit standards for each sector to support carbon market development;
- (iii) Develop reference contract types with standardised terms for carbon trading;
- (iv) Provide basic information to support the implementation of greenhouse gas inventories at the local level (province / city).

Target policies

The expected outcomes aim to realise the tasks of the Carbon Market Development Project in Vietnam.

➤ Focus theme 2.4.3: Greenhouse gas inventory associated with 1 million hectares of high-quality, low-emission rice project

Why is it important?

Applying circular principles in agriculture has the potential to reduce Vietnam's carbon footprint, reduce waste, while creating additional employment opportunities and promoting the development of green, low-carbon and circular agriculture. In Vietnam, rice production accounts for 19% of total national greenhouse gas emissions. Recently, the Government of Vietnam approved the project "Sustainable development of 1 million hectares specialising in high quality and low emission rice production linked to green growth in the Mekong Delta by 2030". The total estimated capital required to implement the project is approximately USD 650 million, divided into 2 phases: (i) Phase 1 requires approximately USD 60 million to consolidate the invested area of 180,000 hectares of the VnSAT project; (ii) Phase 2 requires USD 590 million to expand approximately 820,000 hectares of high quality and low emission specialty rice areas.

The project is particularly important in the direction of transforming sustainable rice production in the Mekong Delta and forming and developing large-scale, long-term stable concentrated raw material areas to ensure sustainable agricultural quality, sustainable and effective. The project aims to reduce input costs by 30%, contributing to a reduction in rice production costs for farming households of about VND9,500 billion; increase the profit margin of rice farmers by 50%; and contribute to a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 10%.

During the implementation of the project, there will be a number of new policies in line with global trends that will be piloted, such as paying carbon credits based on results for 1 million hectares of high-quality, low-emission rice. related to green growth, circular production, multi-value exploitation in rice production with policies and mechanisms on investment or credit with the aim of attracting enterprises in the field of rice production and processing. Therefore, a greenhouse gas inventory to implement results-based carbon credit payments for 1 million hectares of high-quality, low-emission rice has practical and important implications.

Policy landscapes

- 1) "Master Programme for Sustainable Agricultural Development Adapted to Climate Change in the Mekong Delta until 2030, Vision until 2045";
- 2) Project "Sustainable development of 1 million hectares of high quality, low emission specialty rice associated with green growth in the Mekong Delta by 2030";
- 3) Project "Modernisation of Irrigation Systems for Transformation and Sustainable Agricultural Development in Ecological Sub-regions of the Mekong Delta"

Expected outcomes and target policy

Expected outcomes

(i) Develop a toolkit for monitoring greenhouse gases in rice production for each different production method (e.g. 1P5G, AWD,...).

(ii) Analyse the costs and benefits of investing in rice production infrastructure systems to reduce emissions, to ensure economic, social and environmental efficiency at the time of investment decisions.

Target policies

The expected outcomes are to implement the tasks of the Carbon Market Development Project in Vietnam; to implement the plan to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in the agricultural sector.

➤ Focus theme 2.4.4: Assessing the impact of the European Union's (EU) Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) on industry. Proposing appropriate carbon tax policies.

Why is it important?

From October 2023, the European Union has introduced a cross-border carbon tax mechanism (CBAM - Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism) to ensure fairness in international trade competition and promote the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. The CBAM will impose taxes on products imported into the EU based on the amount of greenhouse gas emissions (direct and indirect) emitted during the production process.

According to the plan, the EU will pilot the CBAM in the period 2023-2025 with 6 types of products, including iron and steel, cement, fertilisers, aluminium, electrical energy and hydrogen. From 2026 and in the long term, when financial measures are applied, Vietnamese enterprises exporting goods on the taxable list (steel, cement, aluminium) will be affected. Therefore, in order to adapt to CBAM, Vietnam needs to further improve relevant policies in the coming period and urgently and soon consider the promulgation of a carbon pricing policy (application of an appropriate carbon tax). Develop the operation of the carbon market and the domestic and international carbon credit exchange and offset mechanism in accordance with the provisions of the law and international treaties. The application of carbon tax needs a specific roadmap to ensure harmony between the interests of the state, enterprises and taxpayers.

Policy landscapes

- 1) Decree on Greenhouse Gas Inventory is shown by Articles 91, 92 and 139 of the Law on Environmental Protection 2020, Decree No. 06/2022/ND-CP on Regulations on the Reduction of Greenhouse Gas Emissions (GHG) and Protection of the Ozone Layer.

- 2) Prime Minister's Decision No. 01/2022/QĐ-TTg, which establishes the list of sectors and facilities emitting GHGs that are required to conduct GHG inventories.
- 3) Project to develop carbon market in Vietnam, preparing for pilot operation of carbon trading floor in 2025, official operation in 2028.

Expected outcomes and target policy

Expected outcomes

(i) Analyse the impact of CBAM on production and business of industries and enterprises in the taxable list;

(ii) Propose carbon tax policy solutions consistent with existing policies, in accordance with Vietnamese context and international regulations.

(iii) Propose policy mechanisms to encourage and support enterprises to set voluntary emission reduction targets and plans, and trade carbon credits to compensate for plant emissions; financial support mechanism for enterprises exporting to Europe.

Target policies

The expected outcomes are to provide a basis for the application of the carbon tax policy, with the aim of amending the Decree on Environmental Protection Fees, thereby reducing the pressure on companies exporting to the EU.

2.5. Other themes

Focus theme 2.5.1: Climate insurance (Environmental Protection Act 2020, climate risk insurance)

Focus theme 2.5.2: Financial mechanism for adaptation to climate change (NAP)

Focus theme 2.5.3: Mechanism for Loss and Damage Fund in Vietnam (Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment)